

Interview DRASSM, Nathalie Huet
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Name: Michaela Florescu
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WP2. Investigating the conservation of WWII wrecks (land or underwater), and more particularly parts made of Al alloys.

- Presentation of the institution

The Département des Recherches Archéologiques Subaquatiques et Sous-marines (DRASSM) is a department of the French Ministry of Culture who manages the underwater and undersea archaeological heritage on French territory.

DRASSM mission is to supervise application of the Code du Patrimoine (French Law for Cultural Heritage) for maritime heritage. It is thus competent for all archaeological research requiring the use of diving. It's competence covers waters in the French ZEE (exclusive economic zone) , which covers approximately 11 million km² worldwide.

DRASSM manages all types of wrecks (e.g, ships, aircrafts) for all historical periods, not only focused on WWII aircraft wrecks.

- Legal framework for underwater wrecks in France

French law recognizes the right to flag for French wrecks, government or military property, in foreign waters. This regulation is in principle recognized at international level after UNESCO Convention 2001, but this convention has not been ratified by all countries.

Flag law is included in maritime law. It means that every ship is under the exclusive jurisdiction of its flag State and, subject to certain reservations, that no other maritime State has legal jurisdiction over ships not flying its flag.

Fluvial & lake waters = land public domain = under SRA (Sevice Régional d'Archéologie), DRAC (Direction Générale des Affaires Culturelles), both being 2 other departements of the French Ministry of Culture.

France has several ongoing procedures against certain States for non-compliance with the law of the flag. For example for French wreck sunk in the ^{16th} century in Florida. Florida follows other different regulations, which make it possible for a commercial company to operate, but has lost it's trial in this occasion.

Asian countries have no legislation concerning this matter, possibility trade cultural heritage recoveries.

New Caledonia: follows it's own legislation for archaeological underwater diving

In principle flag law is the same everywhere for all countries and is meant to be reciprocal.

- Ownership of the wrecks

In France, everything found in the maritime domain belongs to the State, unless it is possible to find the rightful owner or heir.

Concerning WWII wrecks, situations should be rather simple and straightforward, the flag law applies. But it does not always interest the flag State to regain their right.

More complex case of ships that have changed ownership during the war, as they may have a different nationality between the beginning and the end of the war. What prevails is the last known nationality. In general, the nations that have not been victorious in the conflict do not necessarily claim their wrecks; they have been a little more watchful in the last 5-6 years.

This situation is less common for airplanes.

American Navy is mainly interested in finding the bodies and plates of their soldiers, not so much focused on the wreck itself.

What are the rules for ownership of land recoveries ? Nathalie Huet does not know.

For a long time, great lack of interest for WWII wrecks as cultural heritage. Even if definition in the heritage code was quite broad. At sea, concessions given to scrap dealers just after the war, some of which took the opportunity to create personal collections or private museums, ex museums in Normandie along D-Day beaches.

UNESCO Convention concerns boats over 100 years old.

Still some associations that continue to have this scrap dealer's approach, looting, selling parts or wrecks.

- Excavation/recovery authorization for associations

Until about 15 years ago, associations would bring back WWII artefacts from any diving operation on any occasion, excavations were rather random. In the recent years, vigilance has increased for this type of heritage.

All associations have the right to make searches, but these operations must be declared. 2 situation can occur : either targeted excavation on an artefact already known, or prospecting.

The procedure states that an application must be filed with DRASSM, who authorizes or not the recovery/excavation/study operation based on relevance of the request and historical interest of the wreck.

Relevance for authorization: e.g. if the wreck is already known and studied, no authorization. Also refused for example if the wreck is considered as military graveyard or memory repository. DRASSM evaluates the purpose of the operation and the association's goals.

In general, DRASSM prefers to keep wrecks in situ. Association must prove that they are willing and have the means to ensure long term care for the wreck : storage, funding, technical skills. Also sometimes expectations in terms of conservation and restoration.

Unesco Convention prescribes to protect the wrecks in situ, but historically France has not shared this opinion, rather tendency to get artefacts out of the water. Nathalie and her colleagues believe that it is necessary to reduce the recoveries.

In Greece or Malta entire wrecks can be visited underwater, these 2 countries have much less tendency to recover artefacts/wrecks.

In France “culture of looting”, where it seems more “normal” to bring back everything that can be. In France there is also a very important diving culture.

- How to manage wrecks from old recoveries in the museums / associations ?

There are many situations where wrecks from older recoveries, where legal framework has not been entirely respected, are now part of museums collections or under guardianship of associations. How is the situation approached today ? Some of the partners of Procraft find themselves in that situation and are afraid of losing their aircrafts.

DRASSM works with the associations to reintegrate the old wrecks in DRASSM collections. Also ongoing inventories among scrap dealers and in the military museums to identify these situations and solve them.

For everything that is found fortuitously at the present time, DRASSM makes a pedagogical effort and explains how to deal with the situation. DRASSM offers help in understanding and complying with the procedures, such as filling the declaration of discovery, making contact with the owning countries. They also offer help in trying to find a place to deposit objects with deposit agreement.

Example :

Spitfire in Normandy, emergency recovery of the aircraft from a private person. The wreck has been immediately plunged back into the Caen basin. The aircraft was a British aircraft with an Australian pilot. UK was not interested in recovering the wreck, but ultimately the wreck went to Australia at the Royal Australian Airforce Museum at Point Cook.

DRASSM is a little more flexible when it comes to the more recent wrecks. The general approach and priority is to bring all shady situations back to normal. DRASSM does not give ownership of a wreck, but can make deposit/long-term loan agreements. In principle, embassies have to be contacted, but as it is not always appropriate, DRASSM takes the responsibility of managing the decisions case by case.

Concerning the private museums, DRASSM doesn't usually take back the litigious wrecks unless there is a sale.

DRASSM encourages to legitimize all unclear situations, especially as there are advantages in having a clear legal framework: the main one being that it is then possible to apply for public/governmental funding to care for the wreck.

But Nathalie is aware that DRASSM itself has not always been very clear in the past, especially with regard to liabilities.

In France, the 3 SRA Pays de la Loire, Normandie and Grand Est are more demanding than the other SRAs on these issues. But, generally speaking, SRAs are less strict than DRASSM and would concede legal ownership to the current custodian of the wreck, without enquiring much about the past.

- DRASSM expectation in terms of conservation and restoration

Nathalie does not advocate for bringing back wrecks to new condition. In her opinion, it is an illusion to aim for that goal when an aircraft has been under water. It is very difficult technically speaking and would most of the time require remaking a lot of parts.

For her, the general appearance and condition of wrecks should reflect their history and their stay in marine environment.

In the case of fortuitous discoveries, if there is no solid candidate for guardianship, DRASSM puts the wreck back into the sea.